

Aerodynamic Design and Performance Analysis of a Micro-Scale Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine Blades along with endplate addition through multi-fidelity computational fluid dynamics tools

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ABSTRACT

The transition toward renewable energy sources has positioned wind energy as a critical technology for achieving global carbon neutrality targets. While large-scale wind farms dominate current installations, micro-scale horizontal-axis wind turbines present significant potential for distributed energy generation in remote and rural areas. This study presents a comprehensive methodology for designing micro-scale wind turbine blades through comparative analysis of three computational approaches: classical Blade Element Momentum Theory (BEMT), QBlade software, and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations, selecting the designing methodology based on a trade-off between accuracy and computational cost. A numerical campaign on airfoil assessment was conducted to identify optimal blade geometries, with performance evaluated based on power coefficient distribution, peak power output, and cut-in wind speed. The investigation reveals that CFD simulations predict 23.34% higher power coefficients at peak compared to BEMT and 22.46% compared to QBlade due to three-dimensional effects including rotational stall delay. The addition of endplates to the optimized blade design demonstrates significant improvements in performance. This multi-fidelity approach provides a robust framework for micro-scale wind turbine design, balancing computational efficiency with accuracy requirements, and studies the impact of adding endplates.

1. Introduction

The global imperative for carbon emission reduction has accelerated the deployment of renewable energy technologies. In this global context wind energy presents itself as a key factor for achieving international climate targets. The Paris Agreement of 2015 established the goal of limiting global temperature increase to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels [1], subsequently strengthened by the Glasgow Climate Pact in 2021, which aims for a 1.5°C limit [2]. To meet these targets, countries worldwide have committed to a decarbonization goal, with China targeting carbon neutrality by 2060 [3] and the European Union by 2050 [4] among others.

Wind energy capacity has recently experienced a continuous growth, with global installations continuing to expand both onshore and offshore [5]. However, the benefits of wind energy must extend beyond large-scale centralized wind farms in order to encompass distributed generation systems that can serve remote and rural communities with a lack of access to the centralized electrical grid or adequate infrastructure for large-scale installations. Micro-scale horizontal-axis wind turbines (HAWT), commonly defined by a rated power output below 1.5 kW [6], represent a critical component of this distributed energy strategy, even being able to be combined with other renewable energy sources such as solar panels [7].

The design philosophy for micro-scale wind turbines fundamentally differs from their large-scale counterparts, emphasizing modularity, simplicity, and reduced maintenance requirements. Traditional pitch control systems, while effective for large turbines, introduce complexity and costs that are often prohibitive for small installations. Consequently, passive optimization strategies focusing on aerodynamic blade design combined with electrical control systems such as Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) have become the preferred approach [8]. The implementation of this control method must be coupled with a sufficiently wide operational range of maximum or near-maximum efficiency to avoid losses associated with reduced efficiency [9]. These systems maximize power extraction by regulating the working tip speed ratio through generator control, eliminating the need for complex mechanical pitch mechanisms.

The aerodynamic design of micro-scale wind turbine blades presents unique challenges that require careful consideration of computational methods and their inherent limitations. The classical Blade Element Momentum Theory (BEMT) has been the cornerstone of wind turbine design due to its computational efficiency and reasonable accuracy, being extensively used in the literature where several different authors use this method in order to optimize the chord and twist distribution along the blade [10, 11], since it has been proven to improve the wind turbine performance respect a non-optimized blade [12]. However, BEMT fundamental assumption of two-dimensional flow neglects significant three-dimensional effects that can impact the wind turbine performance. Recent advances in computational tools have provided alternatives to traditional BEMT approaches aiming to increase the studying fidelity of those three-dimensional

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effects. For instance, the open-source wind turbine design software QBlade [13] incorporates corrections for three-dimensional effects while maintaining computational efficiency. For that reason, QBlade has recently started to be used in the literature as a design tool [14, 15] and validated comparing the results obtained respect to the classical BEMT and experimental data [16, 17]. The corrections included by this software address some of the limitations of classical BEMT by incorporating boundary layer analysis and rotational effects into the momentum theory framework [18]. For cases requiring higher fidelity, three-dimensional Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations can be used in order to capture complex phenomena such as rotational stall delay, tip vortex formation, and blade-wake interactions [12, 19, 20]. These methodologies are often used in the design process [21, 22], allowing to create an optimum design.

The reduced scale of the micro-scale wind turbines allows different methods of improving aerodynamic performance to be proposed, such as surface treatments [23], combining wind turbines in tandem configuration [24] or different blade tip designs relative to the bigger-scale options such as backwards or forwards swept blades [25] and the design of different kind of winglets [26, 27]. Particularly, endplates (the simplest version of a winglet) have been also studied in the case of vertical-axis wind turbines [28].

Yet, to the author's knowledge, the literature does not address the endplates impact in the case of a horizontal-axis wind turbine, being the endplates a feature that could increase the aerodynamic performance of HAWTs without increasing significantly their manufacturing or design costs.

While the literature examines the differences between the analysis methods presented [29, 30], it is necessary to determine a trade-off between their fidelity and computational cost in order to establish an efficient yet functional design methodology, aiming to capture the three-dimensional effects. The present study addresses the critical need for a comprehensive design methodology that systematically compares these computational approaches while optimizing blade geometry for micro-scale HAWTs.

This work develops a multi-fidelity design framework comparing BEMT, QBlade, and CFD methodologies. Within this framework, a systematic optimization of blade geometry is conducted through a numerical campaign. The study also focuses on the quantification of the three-dimensional effects on performance predictions. Finally, effectiveness of endplates will be investigated as a strategy for aerodynamic performance enhancement.

This article first describes the implementation of the BEMT methodology and its three-dimensional corrections in subsection 2.1. Next, the CFD model set up and its meshing and validation are addressed in subsection 2.2. Then, the followed design procedure, starting with the comparison of the different computational methods used and finally the effects of the endplates on the blade performance are presented in section 3. Finally, some concluding remarks are provided in section 4.

2. Methodology

The design and analysis procedures outlined in this study employ various numerical methodologies whose proper configuration and implementation are critical for ensuring reliable results. This section presents the detailed setup and procedures employed for each computational approach.

As it is observed in Figure 1, the design process is divided in different steps. The design and analysis methodologies are described in subsection 2.1 and subsection 2.2. Then, the methods are compared in subsection 3.1 and a method is selected in order to compute the airfoil assessment study, which is done in subsection 2.3. Finally, a geometry is selected and the effects of adding an endplate are studied in subsection 3.3.

2.1. Blade Element Momentum Theory Implementation

This method discretizes the rotor blades into independent sections, each assumed to generate constant force on the flow field. The theory employs two fundamental induction factors: the axial induction factor (a) and the rotational induction factor (a'), which, together with the air velocity U_∞ and the rotational speed, ωr , define the velocity triangle experienced by each blade section, as observed in Figure 2, creating the relative velocity U_{rel} . These parameters are essential for determining the resultant angle of attack, following established methodologies [31]. This approach inherently neglects three-dimensional flow effects. Additionally, the implementation requires lift and drag coefficient databases as functions of angle of attack for each of the blade section studied. The angle of attack has been obtained for this paper through XFOil [32], which calculates lift by means of an inviscid linear-vorticity panel method, whereas drag considers the viscous effects through a distributed source model superimposed on the airfoil and wake geometry. These databases allow to calculate the loads at each section. To enhance accuracy, Prandtl tip loss and Glauert corrections were implemented, aiming to account for finite blade number effects and induction factors exceeding the critical value a_c (usually defined as 1/3), respectively [31].

Furthermore, other corrections aiming to model three-dimensional effects can be added. QBlade [13], an open-source wind turbine design and analysis platform, incorporates a three-dimensional correction to classical BEMT. This correction employs boundary layer equation magnitude analysis for high aspect ratio rotating blades under both attached and separated flow conditions, yielding simplified equations that are integrated into BEMT computations without significant computational cost increase [18]. This software also allows to create 3D models of blades optimizing the chord and twist distributions based on the BEMT method.

The classical BEMT and the QBlade implementation both allow to assess the wind turbine performance by calculating the power and torque coefficients, which are dimensionless values of power and torque, as a function of tip speed ratio, a relation between the rotational and lineal

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the followed workflow.

Figure 2: Velocity triangle configuration established by BEMT methodology.

172 speeds perceived by the blade tip. These coefficients are
 173 defined, respectively, in Equation 1 and Equation 2 and the
 174 tip speed ratio in Equation 3.

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_P &= \frac{W}{\frac{1}{2}\rho AU_\infty^3}, & C_Q &= \frac{Q}{\frac{1}{2}\rho AU_\infty^2 r}, & \lambda &= \frac{\omega R}{U_\infty}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1} \tag{2} \tag{3}$$

2.2. Computational Fluid Dynamics

176 While CFD provides enhanced fidelity in three-dimensional
 177 flow modeling compared to BEMT, this advantage comes
 178 at increased computational expense. For achieving this
 179 increase in fidelity, the full geometry must be solved in a
 180 three-dimensional manner, omitting hybrid models such as
 181 the actuator disk. The model set up and meshing strategy will
 182 be discussed and validated using a NREL reference case.
 183

2.2.1. CFD Simulation Setup

184 The computational fluid simulations are performed using
 185 the software StarCCM+. Multiple control volumes were
 186 established to ensure well-defined computational domains,
 187 as illustrated in Figure 3 and Figure 4. The configuration
 188 for a three-bladed HAWT employs a third of a cylinder as
 189 the domain imposing periodic boundary conditions phased
 190

at 120°, neglecting tower effects for computational simplifi- 191
 cation. The fluid is modeled as dry air at sea level conditions. 192

The main factors affecting the turbine performance are 193
 the wind speed and the turbine rotational speed. The desired 194
 flow velocity is imposed as normal to the domain inlet, while 195
 atmospheric pressure at sea level is imposed at the outlet, as 196
 seen in Figure 4. The curved sides of the domain are estab- 197
 lished as symmetry planes. This symmetry condition, while 198
 not physically representative, is commonly employed to 199
 simulate extended domains while avoiding wall interaction 200
 effects [33]. Simulations are run considering a steady-state 201
 approach, modeling the rotation of the wind turbine through 202
 Moving Reference Frame (MRF) methodology, applied to 203
 the innermost volume observed in Figure 3 and Figure 4. 204
 Domain dimensions were established to ensure convergence 205
 by minimizing boundary condition influence on the region 206
 of interest. 207

A segregated solver was employed given Mach numbers 208
 below 0.3, enabling incompressible flow assumptions. 209
 Flow modeling utilized Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes 210
 (RANS) equations under steady-state conditions. The $k - \omega$ 211
 SST turbulence model was selected based on the literature 212
 [34, 19]. The described methodology is consistent with 213
 established practices [35]. 214

2.2.2. Mesh Generation

215 The domain is discretized using polyhedral cells. The 216
 mesh includes a 1.4 mm global thickness prism layer mesh 217
 consisting on seven layers as well as local refinements at 218
 the blade surface and its surroundings, including the rotat- 219
 ing region. The surface refinement consists on increasing 220
 the maximum curvature allowed for the cells on the blade 221
 surface to a value of 168 and imposing its cell size to be 222
 a 1% respect to the cell size imposed on the global domain. 223
 The volumetric controls can be seen in Figure 3 and Figure 4 224
 and consist on reducing the cell size to a 15% of the global 225

Figure 3: CFD simulation domain and refinement volumes (not scale) side view

Figure 4: CFD simulation domain and refinement volumes (not scale) perspective view

	Mesh 1	Mesh 2	Mesh 3
Base Size [m]	0.24375	0.1875	0.15
C_p [-]	0.3638	0.3681	0.3798
Error	-	1.19 %	3.18 %
Number of elements	2×10^6	4×10^6	8×10^6
Difference	-	170.47 %	176.13 %

Table 1
GCI study results.

domain cell size for the outermost volume and to a 5% for the innermost one.

Grid Convergence Index (*GCI*) analysis was conducted to quantify the error relative to the asymptotic solution. This methodology involves multiple simulations with varying mesh densities in order to determine the order of approximation of the solution and to establish appropriate base size for maintaining the desired error tolerance [36]. The results of these simulations can be seen in Table 1, the refinement rate chosen is 1.25. Both the error in power coefficient and the difference in number of elements are defined respect to the previous mesh.

Asymptotic range validation of the obtained results can be confirmed through the expression shown in Equation 4 [37], confirming the abatement of discretization error.

$$\frac{GCI_{23}}{rr^p GCI_{12}} = 0.998 \sim 1. \quad (4)$$

Based on the simulations results, the order of approximation of the solution can be calculated. Next, a desired error of 5% is imposed. The required base cell size for keeping the error within the desired range can be calculated, as described in the literature [36], to be 0.178 meters. The final mesh, consisting on 6×10^6 cells, can be seen in Figure 5.

While this analysis was performed for a representative geometry, the calculated base size was applied to all simulations due to the equivalent nature of the flow phenomena across configurations.

In order to ensure proper wall resolution and mesh quality, a Wall Y^+ and cell aspect ratio analysis is performed. The distribution demonstrates values of Wall Y^+ below 5 for all cells and below 1 for the 57.42% of the cells, confirming mesh adequacy according to established criteria [38]. In case of the cell aspect ratio, all the cells have a value over 0.05, having the 75.53% of the cells a value above 0.95.

2.2.3. CFD Model Validation

The validation of the CFD model was conducted using the NREL Phase VI rotor geometry. Scaled computational domains were defined to preserve consistent blade-to-volume ratios, and prism-layer remeshing was applied to ensure that the Wall Y^+ values remained within the recommended range. The selected experimental dataset corresponds to Sequence I, characterized by a series of wind speeds ranging from 5 m/s to 24 m/s, a constant rotational speed of 72 rpm, and zero yaw angle. This sequence was selected since it represents the conditions studied in this paper. Numerical calculations of the pressure coefficient distribution along the blade chord at selected spanwise positions were compared against available experimental measurements [39] at three different working tip speed ratios. Defining the pressure coefficient as seen in Equation 5, the comparisons are presented in Figure 6. The pressure coefficient distributions along the chord calculated by the CFD show the same tendencies of those measured experimentally, demonstrating the capability of the CFD to properly estimate the experimental data and tendencies at different working conditions.

$$c_{PressRot} = \frac{P - P_0}{\frac{1}{2} \rho [U_\infty^2 + (\omega r)^2]} \quad (5)$$

In addition to the pressure coefficient distributions, the power coefficient vs tip speed ratio curve was calculated from the computational pressure coefficient data following the procedure established in the experimental report [39]. The results, which can be seen in Figure 7, show a similar power coefficient distribution for the different calculation

Figure 5: CFD mesh side view close-up to the interest zone. Additional close-ups to the blade refinement volume and prism layer

(a) Pressure coefficient distribution along chord for 46.6% span

(b) Pressure coefficient distribution along chord for 80% span

Figure 6: Pressure Coefficient distribution along the chord for CFD and experimental calculations at different span % at $\lambda = 1.67$, $\lambda = 4.02$ and $\lambda = 8.04$

286 methods. The most noticeable discrepancies appear in $\lambda =$
 287 5.02 and $\lambda = 5.74$, which are a 10.03% lower and a 9.45%
 288 higher respectively when calculated from the CFD extracted
 289 data.

2.3. Numerical Campaign

290 A numerical campaign was formulated to systematically
 291 evaluate all feasible design configurations. The campaign
 292 framework was structured to assess three primary perfor-
 293 mance criteria:
 294

- 295 • Peak power coefficient maximization.
- 296 • Power coefficient distribution as a function of tip
 297 speed ratio, targeting low stall tip speed ratios, mean-
 298 ing a lower maximum rotational speed for a given
 299 wind speed, thus increasing overall security, while

300 maintaining an adequate optimum operational range to
 301 mitigate efficiency losses associated with Maxi-
 302 mum Power Point Tracker (MPPT) system imperfec-
 303 tions [9].

- 304 • Torque coefficient at a tip speed ratio of zero, serving
 305 as an indicator of cut-in wind speed.

306 The cut-in wind speed is calculated as shown in Equa-
 307 tion 6

$$V_{ci} = \sqrt{\frac{2Q_{ci}}{\rho A C_Q R}}, \quad (6)$$

NREL Phase VI C_p vs λ for different calculation methods

Figure 7: Power coefficient versus tip speed ratio curves for the NREL Phase VI blade geometry obtained using different calculation methods.

 Bergey Blade c_p vs λ for different methods

Figure 8: Power coefficient versus tip speed ratio curves for the Bergey blade geometry obtained using different computational methods

where Q_{ci} represents the generator starting torque, assumed to be 0.5 Nm for this analysis. The torque coefficient c_Q is determined at zero tip speed ratio according to Equation 7.

$$c_Q = \frac{Q|_{\lambda=0}}{\frac{1}{2} \rho A U_\infty^2 R}. \quad (7)$$

The design variable will be the airfoil used along the span. The same airfoil will be used along the whole span, as commonly used in the design of micro-scale wind turbines [35, 40]. The different airfoils are obtained from an airfoil database [41], filtering to obtain those designed specifically for wind turbines and a NACA0015, making a total of 33 different airfoils. The selected families are the Bergey, Selig, Althaus, Martin-Hepperle, Jacobs, and Wortmann [42, 43].

The following design constraints were imposed to ensure practical feasibility:

- Rotor radius of 0.8 m, representing a balance between compactness and power output capability (estimated maximum of 1 kW) [44].
- Blade number as three, providing a compromise between power extraction, operational stability, and manufacturing costs [45].
- Design tip speed ratio as 3.0, selected to enhance low wind speed performance while reducing structural loading requirements [46].
- Solidity at the root lower than one, established to prevent inter-blade interference given the tendency for chord increase at the root during optimization and achieved by imposing a chord at the root of 0.2 m.

The chord and twist distributions along the span for the different geometries are not considered a variable since will be optimized based on the BEMT method.

3. Results

This section presents the results obtained through the different methodologies employed in this study. Initially, a comparative analysis between computational methods is conducted to establish the most suitable approach for the numerical campaign. Subsequently, the campaign results and associated analyses are presented and discussed. Finally, endplates are implemented in the geometry aiming to improve the blade performance.

3.1. Comparative Analysis of Computational Methods

To evaluate the performance and computational cost of the different approaches, a reference blade geometry based on the Bergey BW-3 airfoil was selected for comparative analysis. The power coefficient characteristics of this blade were calculated using the three methodologies described in the previous section. The comparative results are presented in Figure 8.

The observed discrepancies between the computational methods can be attributed to three-dimensional flow effects, which are neglected by the BEMT and simplified by QBlade. These effects result in significant differences in the predicted power coefficient distribution and peak value: 23.34% between CFD and BEMT, and 22.46% between CFD and QBlade, being the CFD the method presenting a higher peak power coefficient. The three-dimensional flow structures responsible for these discrepancies are visualized in Figure 9.

The three-dimensional effects observed are primarily associated with the phenomenon of rotational stall delay, whereby the airfoil stall condition is postponed due to centrifugal and Coriolis forces acting on the rotating blade. This mechanism has been demonstrated to be relevant in wind turbine applications [47]. Figure 9, illustrates wall shear stress streamlines with pressure coefficient colormap at the design tip speed ratio ($\lambda = 3.0$). It is observed that the flow

Figure 9: Wall shear stress streamlines with pressure coefficient colormap on the suction side of the Bergye blade at $\lambda = 3$

Figure 10: Power coefficient versus tip speed ratio curves for the three selected candidate geometries

Figure 11: Airfoil profiles of the three numerical campaign candidate geometries

373 detaches from the blade near the leading edge on the suction
 374 side, corresponding to the region of maximum suction, and
 375 reattaches at higher chord values. This behavior is associated
 376 with the formation of a recirculation zone, indicative of complex
 377 three-dimensional flow structures. Such flow features
 378 enhance suction, leading to higher power coefficients than
 379 those predicted by methods that neglect three-dimensional
 380 effects, as illustrated in Figure 8.

381 From a computational cost perspective, the CFD simulations
 382 required an average of 27 hours to generate complete
 383 power coefficient curves when run on a 15-core cluster,
 384 representing a computational cost approximately 810 times
 385 higher than that of BEMT or QBlade, which completed the
 386 same calculations in approximately 2 minutes on average
 387 using an 8-core laptop.

388 Considering the trade-off between computational accu-
 389 racy and cost, and acknowledging that the significance of
 390 three-dimensional effects has been established, QBlade was
 391 selected as the primary computational tool for the numerical
 392 campaign on turbine blade airfoil assessment. This decision
 393 was based on its substantially lower computational cost
 394 compared to CFD, while still considering three-dimensional
 395 effects, albeit in a simplified form.

3.2. Numerical Campaign Results and Analysis

396 A numerical campaign to evaluate the suitability of
 397 33 different airfoils for the design of turbine blades was
 398 conducted using QBlade, according to the methodology
 399 described in section 2.

400 Based on the selection criteria established in the method-
 401 ology section, the three highest-performing geometries were
 402 identified from the campaign results. These candidate con-
 403 figurations demonstrate superior aerodynamic performance
 404 characteristics based on the criteria previously established,
 405 as illustrated in Figure 10.

406 The airfoil profiles corresponding to each candidate ge-
 407 ometry are presented in Figure 11. It should be noted that
 408 the blade nomenclature refers to the airfoil family employed
 409 in each design configuration.
 410

3.2.1. Cut-in Wind Speed Analysis

411 The remaining performance criterion evaluated for the
 412 candidate geometries is the cut-in wind speed, with prefer-
 413 ence given to configurations exhibiting the lowest values.
 414

415 The lowest cut-in speed was achieved by the Jacobs
 416 blade, featuring a USNPS4 airfoil, with 3.10 m/s. The high-
 417 est cut-in speed was the Selig blade, featuring a SG6041
 418 airfoil and a value of 3.59 m/s. The Bergye blade, consist-
 419 ing of the BW-3 airfoil, achieved a cut-in speed of 3.12 m/s.

3.2.2. Final Geometry Selection

420 Following comprehensive evaluation of the aerodynamic
 421 performance metrics and cut-in wind speed characteristics,
 422 the Bergye blade configuration emerges as the selected de-
 423 sign candidate. This selection is justified by its performance
 424 characteristics, including the lowest stall tip speed ratio, a
 425 similar peak power coefficient respect to the other candi-
 426 dates, and competitive cut-in wind speed performance.
 427

Figure 12: Chord and twist distributions along the span of the Bergely blade

Figure 13: Endplate geometric specifications

Figure 14: Power coefficient versus tip speed ratio curves for Bergely blade with different wingtip configurations

the turbine operational behavior across different tip speed ratios.

The most notable effect observed is the increase of the negative slope in the power coefficient curve for tip speed ratios exceeding the design value. This characteristic is advantageous from a safety perspective, as it reduces the maximum achievable rotational velocity. Additionally, the endplate configuration results in an increase in the peak power coefficient of a 2.3%. The increase in peak power coefficient provided by the endplate is of the same order of magnitude as other tip treatments reported in the literature [25, 26]. However, the effects on the power coefficient distribution are not observed with other types of wingtip configurations. Regarding the cut-in speed there are not relevant changes. It is important to consider that adding an endplate would mean an increase of inertia, so the cut-in speeds could be increased.

In order to determine the reasons behind the increase in peak power coefficient, several flow analysis are performed. Firstly, the torque coefficient along the radius is shown in Figure 15, indicating an increase in the torque generated towards the tip when adding the endplate.

The enhanced torque generation is further corroborated by the pressure coefficient distribution analysis on the blade suction surface, as shown in Figure 16, where an increase in suction can be observed.

The observed improvements in both pressure coefficient and tip torque generation are attributed to the endplate ability to suppress tip vortex formation at the blade tip, effectively relocating the vortical structures to the upper region of the endplate. This phenomenon can be visualized through wall shear stress streamlines superposed to the pressure coefficient distribution already shown, as presented in Figure 17, where it is shown how the flow is attach for the whole blade when adding an endplate.

These visualizations demonstrate that the endplate size is a critical factor in its performance. Undersizing the endplate could result in decreased efficiency due to the proximity

The optimized chord and twist distributions along the blade span, obtained through QBlade BEMT-based optimization algorithm, are presented in Figure 12. These distributions represent the geometric parameters that maximize aerodynamic efficiency while satisfying the design constraints imposed during the optimization process.

3.3. Effects on Performance due to Endplate Addition

Endplates are flat surfaces attached to the blade tip. Their main objective is to prevent the formation of recirculation vortexes at the blade tip, thereby increasing the torque generation and consequently improving the power coefficient.

To enhance the fidelity of the computational simulations, additional geometric features including a hemispherical nose and a cylindrical nacelle were incorporated into the model. Preliminary analysis confirmed that these features have negligible impact on the calculated power coefficient curves, while providing a more realistic representation of the complete turbine geometry.

The chosen endplate is illustrated in Figure 13.

The aerodynamic impact of the endplate implementation on the power coefficient characteristics is presented in Figure 14. The results demonstrate significant modifications in

Figure 15: Spanwise distribution of torque coefficient for different wingtip configurations at $\lambda = 3$

Figure 16: Pressure coefficient distribution at the tip of the blade suction side with (left) and without (right) endplate at $\lambda = 3$

Figure 17: Wall shear stress streamlines with pressure coefficient colormap at the tip of the blade suction side with (left) and without (right) endplate at $\lambda = 3$

Figure 18: Velocity magnitude colormap with streamlines in spanwise view at $\lambda = 7$ for configurations without (top) and with (bottom) endplate

489 of tip vortices to the blade surface, negatively impacting
 490 aerodynamic performance. Conversely, oversizing the end-
 491 plate could introduce unnecessary structural loads due to
 492 increased weight without providing additional aerodynamic
 493 benefits, as the tip vortex effects on the blade would remain
 494 unchanged.

495 The modification in power coefficient vs. tip speed ratio
 496 distribution can be explained through flow physics analysis.
 497 In the baseline configuration without endplates, flow recir-
 498 culation around the blade tip enhances the radial velocity
 499 component. The endplate implementation suppresses this
 500 recirculation, consequently reducing the radial flow com-
 501 ponent. At elevated tip speed ratios, flow separation occurs
 502 at the nose region, generating vortical structures. The re-
 503 duced radial flow component allows the vortical structures
 504 to develop and extend until reaching the blade pressure side,
 505 negatively affecting the blade performance, as illustrated in
 506 Figure 18.

4. Concluding Remarks

507 This study presents an original comprehensive method-
 508 ology for the design and analysis of micro-scale horizon-
 509 tal-axis wind turbines blades, demonstrating the critical im-
 510 portance of computational method selection and three-
 511 dimensional effects consideration in achieving optimal aero-
 512 dynamic performance.

513 The systematic comparison of the traditional BEMT
 514 formulation, QBlade, and CFD methodologies reveals sig-
 515 nificant performance prediction differences, with CFD sim-
 516 ulations indicating 23.34% higher power coefficients com-
 517 pared to classical BEMT and 22.46% compared to QBlade.
 518 This disparity stems from three-dimensional effects, particu-
 519 larly rotational stall delay, which are inadequately captured
 520 by two-dimensional assumptions inherent in BEMT. The
 521

522 QBlade software, incorporating 3D corrections, provides an
523 intermediate solution that balances computational efficiency
524 with improved accuracy, making it suitable for initial design
525 optimization phases. In terms of computational cost, using
526 QBlade results in a cost of approximately 810 times less than
527 using CFD in the design phase.

528 The numerical campaign utilizing 33 airfoils success-
529 fully identified optimal blade configurations. The Bergey
530 BW-3 airfoil emerged as the superior choice, demonstrating
531 the lowest stall tip speed ratio and favorable cut-in wind
532 speed of 3.12 m/s while maintaining a similar peak power
533 coefficient respect to the other candidates. This systematic
534 approach proves effective design decisions, providing quan-
535 titative performance metrics across diverse airfoil geome-
536 tries.

537 The addition of endplates to the optimized blade design
538 yields substantial improvements in both power coefficient
539 magnitude and distribution characteristics. The endplate ef-
540 fectively mitigates tip vortex formation, redirecting flow re-
541 circulation away from the blade tip and increasing tangential
542 force generation. Most significantly, the endplate reduces the
543 stall tip speed ratio, reducing the maximum rotational speed,
544 thus increasing overall safety. This passive enhancement, in-
545 novative in the field of the horizontal-axis wind turbines, re-
546 quires minimal additional manufacturing complexity while
547 providing measurable performance benefits.

548 The investigation confirms that three-dimensional ef-
549 fects play a crucial role in micro-scale wind turbine per-
550 formance. CFD visualizations reveal complex recirculation
551 zones that cannot be predicted by two-dimensional analysis.
552 The quantification of these effects through wall shear stress
553 streamlines provides valuable insights into the underlying
554 flow physics governing wind turbine performance.

555 The developed multi-fidelity design framework offers a
556 practical approach for micro-scale wind turbine optimiza-
557 tion, beginning with efficient QBlade-based numerical stud-
558 ies and culminating in a CFD analysis. This original method-
559 ology addresses the computational cost-accuracy trade-off
560 inherent in wind turbine design, providing designers with
561 a systematic approach for achieving optimal performance
562 within practical constraints.

563 While this study provides significant advances in micro-
564 scale wind turbine design methodology, several limitations
565 warrant acknowledgment. The blade optimization was per-
566 formed using BEMT-based methods, potentially limiting
567 the consideration of three-dimensional effects during the
568 initial design phase. Moreover, any unsteady effect as well
569 as the tower shadowing or yawed wind effects have also
570 been neglected. Future research should investigate CFD-
571 based optimization approaches, despite their computational
572 intensity, and more complex and complete wind turbine
573 models along with experimental validation.

574 The results presented demonstrate that careful considera-
575 tion of computational methods and three-dimensional effects
576 can yield substantial performance improvements in micro-
577 scale wind turbine design. The methodology developed pro-
578 vides a foundation for future research in distributed wind

energy systems, supporting the broader transition toward
sustainable energy infrastructure.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Néstor Alcañiz: Conceptualization, Methodology, Soft-
ware, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft. **Pau Varela:**
Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. **Pedro Quin-
tero:** Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. **Roberto
Navarro:** Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision.

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List of Symbols

Greek symbols

λ	Tip Speed Ratio	611
ω	Rotor angular velocity	612
θ	Blade twist angle	613
ρ	Density	614

Roman symbols

A	Rotor Swept Area	616
a	Axial induction factor	617

618	a'	Tangential induction factor
619	c	Blade chord
620	c_Q	Torque coefficient
621	C_P	Power coefficient
622	$C_{PressRot}$	Pressure coefficient of a rotating body
623	P	Pressure
624	p	Order of approximation of the solution
625	Q	Torque
626	R	Rotor radius
627	r	Radial position
628	rr	Mesh Refinement Rate
629	U_∞	Wind speed
630	x	Non-dimensional radial coordinate

631 Acronyms

632	BEMT	Blade Element Momentum Theory
633	CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
634	DOE	Design of Experiments
635	FFD	Full Factorial Design
636	GCI	Grid Convergence Index
637	HAWT	Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine
638	NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory

639 Subscripts

640	0	Reference value
641	ci	Cut-in value
642	rel	Relative
643	tip	Blade tip

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